

Research on Emergency Capability Assessment

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ABSTRACT

At present, the frequent occurrence of emergencies has threatened the safety of people's lives and property. The complexity and dynamics of emergencies determine the difficulty for the government as a single entity to deal with in emergency management. The active participation of non-governmental organizations, including social organizations, and the realization of the coordination and coupling with government departments are conducive to the improvement of emergency management capability in all aspects and the whole process.

KEYWORDS: *emergency capacity assessment; coordination*

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I. INTRODUCTION

Since the founding of the People's Republic of China 70 years ago, China has created a miracle of rapid economic development and people's living standards have been greatly improved. However, China is a country with a high frequency of natural disasters. For example, In 2019, natural disasters caused a total of 130 million people to be affected, with 909 people dead or missing, and direct economic losses of 327.09 billion yuan. In addition, all kinds of accidents and risks are intertwined and prone to occur, threatening the safety of people's lives and property. It has become an important responsibility of governments at all levels to improve the ability of emergency management to prevent and reduce emergencies and their losses. At the fourth plenary session of the 19th central committee of the communist party of China (CPC), it was proposed to "build an emergency management system that is unified in command, highly specialized, responsive, and interconnected from top to bottom, and optimize the national emergency management capacity system". Xi pointed out that strengthening the emergency management system and capacity building is an urgent and long-term task. However, at the beginning of the outbreak of novel coronavirus in 2020, the problems of the emergency response system in early warning, response, material reserve and other aspects exposed the shortcomings and deficiencies in China's emergency management. Therefore, it has become an urgent research problem to improve the comprehensive emergency management capacity of public emergencies.

II. Theoretical analysis and literature review

Emergency capacity assessment is an important topic of emergency management research (Chen et al., 2011; Zhang,

2015), is the most important component of national security strategy (Pruyt et al., 2013; Mennen et al., 2015). Different governments have different performances in the response to emergencies. The assessment of emergency capacity is conducive to the government to find inner gaps and provide a basis for external supervision, which greatly promotes the improvement of the government's emergency response capacity (Ling, 2010). In 2016, ISO published the guideline to capacity assessment for safety and resilience emergency management, which indicates that the world is increasingly paying attention to emergency capacity assessment (Lindbom et al., 2018). In 1997, the United States federal emergency management agency developed an indicator system for assessing emergency preparedness at the state, territorial, island and county levels, and carried out a comprehensive assessment (Zhang, 2010). In the early stage, Chinese scholars carried out the assessment of the emergency capacity of single disaster, such as earthquake protection (Chen, 1997; Zhang et al., 2004), and also developed a comprehensive assessment of overall disaster management capacity (Zhu and Hu, 2006; Han, 2007), Other scholars have established dynamic evaluation (Douglas and Duncan, 2002) and process-oriented evaluation index system (Chen et al., 2011; Tian et al., 2014). Zhang (2009) proposed to develop a multi-level emergency capability assessment model applicable to the country, region, city, community and town according to the current situation of China's emergency system, and carried out the rural emergency response capability assessment from three dimensions including self-rescue and mutual rescue of villagers (Zhang, 2015). In recent years, more studies have

focused on the assessment of the emergency capability of an important component of disaster or emergency management, such as critical infrastructure (Zhu et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2017), various traffic emergencies (Liu et al., 2014; Lei et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2018; Lu and Huang, 2018) assessment of emergency capability. Even the assessment of the emergency capability of all kinds of disasters (Wang and Cao, 2018), still fails to jump out of the research framework of the assessment of the emergency capability of a single subject of the government.

It is difficult for a single entity, such as the government, social organizations and enterprises, to bear the cost of emergency response independently (Li et al., 2020). After responding to each emergency, the emergency management system and mechanism are further improved. In view of the reflection on the heavy losses caused by emergency, scholars emphasize that the governance of emergency should be changed from single subject governance to multiple governance (Fathi et al., 2020; Tang, 2018; Zhang, 2019; Hu, 2020). Community, social organizations and the public are becoming more important in emergency management, such as improving the public for risk identification and prevention ability, makes the risk disappear in the bud (Chan, 2018).when the coronavirus outbreaks, a large number of protective materials "lying in" temporary warehouse in somewhere of the Red Cross, however, medical institutions are desperately lacking (Li et al., 2020), so including social organizations and the public, collaborative governance is an important aspect of improving the capacity of emergency.

III. Achieving better emergency capacity assessments

The emergency management system bears the important responsibility of preventing and defusing major security risks, which can timely responding to various emergencies. Emergency management is an important part of the country's governance system and capacity. The building of the emergency management system and capacity is conducive to ensuring people's well-being and building a safer China, and is an important part of improving social

governance. Emergency capacity assessment is an important prerequisite for emergency capacity building, which is conducive to identifying weak links, analyzing causes, identifying gaps, and providing directional guidance for improving emergency management so as to achieve continuous improvement. The research of emergency capacity assessment are relatively abundant, but only considered the emergency capability assessment for government, however, the development of emergency is complex, demand for emergency management supplies and personnel also show explosive growth, beyond the capability of the government, effectively deal with all kinds of emergency needs to make full use of social resources, including all kinds of social organizations, the masses of collaborative work, therefore, considering multi-agent coordination in the establishment of the evaluation index system of emergency capability is in line with the new development of the current emergency management theory and complements the deficiency of the current emergency capability evaluation.

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